

Real-Time Flood Water Segmentation with Deep Neural Networks

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Abstract—Nowadays, extreme floods pose severe threats to human lives and infrastructure, necessitating effective flood disaster management plans and systems. In this paper, we address the crucial need of real-time flood monitoring by leveraging computer vision models. To this end, benchmark deep neural networks are trained on the flood water segmentation task, using a novel dataset that was created by combining and annotating flood images from different sources. Our experimental evaluation of two real-world flood videos showcases the potential of computer vision in fast and accurate flood monitoring. Moreover, we investigated the use of semi-supervised training methods to enhance the flood segmentation performance by taking advantage of large unlabeled datasets. Our work emphasizes the potential of applying state-of-the-art big visual data analytics tools to mitigate the devastating impacts of floods on communities worldwide.

Index Terms—Natural Disaster Management (NDM), Flood Water Segmentation, Deep Neural Networks (DNN), Semi-Supervised Learning (SSL)

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing frequency and intensity of extreme flood events have become a significant challenge for communities worldwide, threatening human lives and causing devastating economic losses [1], [2]. The ability to monitor such events effectively and efficiently is vital for Natural Disaster Management (NDM) systems, ensuring timely and accurate alerts that empower local authorities to take swift action [3]. Despite advances in technology, current flood monitoring systems often suffer from limitations in coverage and responsiveness, hindering early detection and mitigation efforts. In response to these challenges, there has been growing interest in the utilization of cutting-edge technologies, like machine learning and computer vision, which can enhance flood monitoring capabilities [4]–[6]. Moreover, developing general-purpose flood datasets that enable DNN segmentation models to easily adapt to diverse landscapes with minimal effort is crucial for enhancing the adaptability and responsiveness of these systems, ensuring fast and reliable insights during critical situations.

Integrating adaptable flood datasets with advanced sensing platforms has the potential to significantly enhance flood monitoring capabilities. Specifically, advancements in embedded computing have enabled the deployment of computer vision models on Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) [5], [6], leveraging their ability to access remote and challenging terrain to capture valuable video footage of flooded regions. When UAVs lack sufficient computing power, this footage can alternatively be processed at the edge. In both cases, flood data can be rapidly and reliably analyzed to support the real-time generation of semantic flood maps. This swift processing capability is crucial for managing the vast amounts of visual data in natural disaster scenarios, meeting the demands of big data analysis. However, deploying a DNN model on such systems is neither trivial nor straightforward. To effectively manage dynamic and unpredictable disaster environments, these systems must be capable of generalizing to previously unseen scenarios without requiring extensive fine-tuning for specific landscapes. This adaptability ensures that flood monitoring systems remain responsive and reliable, even when faced with challenging and rapidly evolving situations.

Although significant progress has been made in semantic segmentation, existing solutions for flood water segmentation often fall short in delivering comprehensive coverage and real-time insights during flood events. Most flood monitoring approaches primarily rely on stationary sensors, limiting their effectiveness in covering vast and remote flooded areas. Furthermore, existing datasets [7], [8] mainly consist of regular water images, failing to capture the complexity of flood scenarios where water spreads across large areas, carrying debris, mud, and soil [4]–[7], [9]. These limitations emphasize the need for a specialized dataset that includes images from diverse sensors, such as UAVs, surveillance cameras, and smartphones, to accurately represent ongoing disaster conditions.

Motivated by these challenges, this study introduces a

novel semi-supervised flood segmentation dataset called FloodSeg. The dataset consists of a supervised component featuring hundreds of high-quality, drone-captured flood images that have been manually annotated to serve as ground truth for training general-purpose flood segmentation DNN models. This supervised data covers a wide range of flood monitoring scenarios. To enhance adaptability, FloodSeg incorporates additional images of diverse landscapes, tailored for challenging scenarios. This further improves the performance of general-purpose flood models in dynamic flood conditions.

II. RELATED WORK

Machine learning techniques, particularly Deep Learning (DL) architectures, can significantly enhance flood disaster management systems by enabling real-time identification, forecasting, and monitoring of large-scale flood events [10]. This capability provides local authorities with a comprehensive view of ongoing situations and delivers early warnings for high-risk areas that require immediate action. As a result, these advancements greatly improve the efficiency of mitigating impacts on human lives, critical infrastructure, property, and minimizing economic disruptions [3].

Computer vision tasks, such as binary semantic segmentation, is proved to be highly effective for flood monitoring systems [11]. In particular, they can easily divide input images into meaningful, semantically consistent regions by classifying each pixel as either flood or background. With their ability to capture complex data representations and achieve high pixel-level precision, segmentation models effectively detect and map flood-affected areas, offering a detailed understanding of water spread across impacted regions. These models often utilize an encoder-decoder architecture, where lightweight Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) serve as encoders to extract hidden patterns from images [9], [12], [13]. The decoder then generates the segmentation mask, enabling accurate and real-time flood detection. This rapid processing capability is crucial for timely decision-making during flood emergencies.

Recent studies in flood water segmentation have introduced several new datasets and innovative methods to improve the accuracy and efficiency of flood detection systems. In [4], the utilized dataset contains predominantly satellite images, which are used for satellite-based disaster monitoring, but cannot be used to train UAV-deployed models that will monitor the flood in real-time. Researchers in [6] have proposed an aerial imagery dataset for post-flood understanding, namely FloodNet, which can be used for the tasks of classification, semantic segmentation, and visual question answering. Nonetheless, these images are captured after

the flooding, and therefore do not depict the ongoing disaster and the flood development.

Additionally, a dataset of urban flooded roadway images has been proposed in [9], and has been used to train and compare benchmark semantic segmentation models. V-Floodnet dataset [7], consists of both regular waterbody images and flood footage. However, their focus was shifted towards utilizing water segmentation to estimate water depth, and thus their method is more suitable for a water surveillance system rather than a real-time flood monitoring tool. A similar dataset consisting of mainly waterbody images was presented in [8]. In [5], the researchers have trained flood segmentation models using FloodNet [6] dataset and compared them in terms of performance and inference speed, which was measured on popular UAV-embedded GPUs. Finally, Flood-Img Database, which is a large flood imagery dataset has been published in [14], though lacking annotations. While these studies make valuable contributions to flood water monitoring, an efficient flood disaster monitoring system requires a novel dataset, primarily consisting of images captured by UAVs. UAVs offer the advantage of providing high-resolution, up-to-date imagery of hard-to-reach or rapidly changing flood zones, enabling more accurate and timely flood assessments.

III. FLOODSEG DATASET

In this section, we introduce the *FloodSeg dataset*, which is specifically created to overcome the limitations of previously published datasets. The FloodSeg dataset is designed to serve two primary purposes. First, it provides high-quality drone-captured images, enabling efficient monitoring of large-scale areas across diverse landscapes and the ongoing flood phenomenon. Second, it offers both supervised and unsupervised options for training segmentation models. The supervised modality includes a wide variety of images to help the models generalize effectively, while the unsupervised modality focuses more on diverse landscapes, enhancing the model's ability to concentrate on challenging domains. Regarding the image selection process, an extensive effort is made to identify and select useful images from well-established, well-known flood datasets, with a particular focus on top-down UAV video footage depicting extreme flood scenes.

Fig. 1. Example images from the FloodSeg training set: the first sample is taken from a publicly available Kaggle dataset, the second is sourced from [9], and the third is from [7].

To enable objective evaluation in the flood segmentation domain, we downloaded and manually annotated two videos from recent catastrophic floods in Greece and Italy. These videos were included in the FloodSeg dataset as test sets, providing a valuable resource for evaluating the performance of any trained flood segmentation model when faced with previously unseen, real-world flood footage. To the best of our knowledge, ours is the first flood dataset to offer annotated real-world videos of destructive flooding, thus simulating a real-use case scenario and offering future researchers benchmark test sets for objective evaluation.

In creating FloodSeg, over 290 UAV images from flood-affected areas were selected, which are publicly available on Kaggle. Additionally, 179 images were sourced from the dataset proposed in [9], most of which were captured from high altitudes, depicting large areas of floodwater. Another 80 images were selected from the dataset presented in [7], focusing on the same characteristics as those mentioned above. For the test set, 567 video frames were selected from a Greek video captured during the 2017 floods in Mandra, Attica region, Greece, and 1,406 video frames were selected from an Italian video captured during the 2023 floods in Emilia Romagna region, Italy.

In total, our supervised training set comprises of 416 images, and our validation set comprises of 132 images. The dataset has been split in a 3:1 ratio, to training and a validation set respectively, while the video frames have been used as test sets. Regarding the semi-supervised part, have been collected over 4600 images. Also, image resolution varies, from 340×221 to 5472×3648 pixels (width \times height). In Figure 1, we present sample images from the FloodSeg training set. These images were combined to form a novel dataset, tailored for training DNN-based flood segmentation models that will be deployed on UAVs, or other edge devices, and will aid in precise monitoring of the flooding.

IV. REAL TIME FLOOD WATER SEMATIC SEGMENTATION

Real-time flood water segmentation is crucial for an effective NDM system, yet it presents several challenges, as previously mentioned. To address these limitations, we detail our flood monitoring system in the following section. Firstly, we discuss the *Flood water segmentation models* employed in this study, focusing on lightweight deep neural networks (DNNs) that are capable of operating in real-time on UAVs and edge devices. Moving forward, explore the *semi-supervised training* approach, which leverages a large pool of unlabeled flood data to improve model performance. Each of these components is essential for developing an efficient and adaptive flood

disaster monitoring system that can provide accurate, real-time insights in dynamic flood scenarios.

A. Supervised Flood Water Segmentation DNN Networks

In general, flood water segmentation involves labeling every image pixel with its corresponding class (flood water or background), serving as an invaluable tool for precise flood mapping. In our study, we opted for lightweight DNN models that are able to operate on UAVs or other edge devices. In this way, we can take advantage of UAV's capacity to monitor regions that cannot be accessed by human rescuers during a disaster. The chosen segmentation models and their properties will be analyzed thoroughly herein.

Fig. 2. CNN-I2I architecture [15].

1) *CNN-I2I*: CNN-I2I [15] is an innovative network that achieves state-of-the-art performance in fast semantic segmentation. This model breaks down into two connected branches, which share the same backbone weights. The main branch can be any benchmark network dedicated to semantic segmentation, while the auxiliary branch is a generative network, tasked to generate the semantic mask for the input image in RGB format. A Discriminator type network in the output of the The auxiliary branch predicts whether the generated RGB mask is real or fake. In this manner, the auxiliary branch (Generator and Discriminator) is trained in an adversarial way, as proposed in [16]. The intuition that lies behind this network is that, features learned by the auxiliary generative branch may be useful for the semantic segmentation branch as well. These features are propagated into the main branch by attention-based synapses. Let M_1 , M_2 be two feature maps from the main and auxiliary branches respectively, then the information that flows into the main branch is computed with the following equation:

$$CA = \text{softmax}(M_1, M_2^T)M_2 \quad (1)$$

In this manner, the main branch can select the features that are deemed important by the attention mechanism. A depiction of the CNN-I2I architecture is displayed in Figure 2. In our work, we implemented CNN-I2I as proposed in [17], with Bisenet [18] being the main branch of the model. Bisenet itself comes with a Resnet18 backbone [19], which is tailored for fast computations.

The model was trained with a multi-task loss function which couples together both semantic segmentation and RGB mask generation objectives.

2) *PSP Net*: PSPnet [12] is a benchmark neural network for semantic segmentation tasks. It utilizes a pyramid pooling module that takes a feature map computed by the backbone network as input and performs pooling at different scales. The resulting feature maps are then concatenated into one (global features), and then concatenated again with the backbone features. Finally, a final convolutional layer predicts the semantic mask. This architecture, which is depicted in Figure 3 can be trained end-to-end, as the pyramid pooling module does not increase much the computational cost. This module has also proved to aid the network in capturing complex scenery context features. This particular network was chosen for the flood water segmentation task due to the complexity of the flood scenes, in which the flood water can surround lots of different objects. In this work, we chose Resnet50 [19] for the backbone network of PSPnet, since it is lightweight enough to maintain near-real-time inference speed when deployed on a commercial Nvidia GPU. It was trained with a Categorical Cross Entropy (CCE) loss, which was implemented pixel-wise and averaged for the whole image.

Fig. 3. PSPNet architecture [12].

3) *PIDNet*: PIDNet [13] is a published model designed to overcome limitations in two-branch segmentation networks, where the direct fusion of high-resolution details and low-frequency contexts can cause fine-grained features to be overwhelmed by surrounding contextual information. To address this, PIDNet introduces a three-branch architecture with complementary functions: the Proportional (P) branch preserves detailed information in high-resolution feature maps, the Integral (I) branch aggregates local and global context to capture long-range dependencies, and the Derivative (D) branch extracts high-frequency features to enhance boundary prediction.

PIDNet is well-suited for flood segmentation tasks due to its ability to balance fine details and broad contextual information. Its Proportional (P) branch preserves high-resolution details, crucial for capturing subtle flood boundaries, while the Integral (I) branch aggregates local and global context to understand large-scale flood

Fig. 4. PIDNet architecture [13].

patterns. The Derivative (D) branch enhances boundary precision by extracting high-frequency features, ensuring accurate differentiation between flooded and non-flooded areas. This multi-branch design enables PIDNet to generalize effectively across diverse environments, making it highly robust for detecting complex and irregular flood regions.

4) *Performance Analysis*: For the supervised setting, all networks were trained using our labeled FloodSeg training dataset. Unless specified otherwise, all three DNN models were trained for a total of 200 epochs with a learning rate of 0.05, following a multi-step learning schedule that reduced the learning rate by a factor of 0.1 at 50, 100, and 150 epochs. Regarding the optimization procedure, we used Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) [20] for CNN-I2I and PSPNet and Adam optimizer [21] for the PIDNet. Image resolution for CN-I2I and PSPNet is set to (640×320) while PIDNet selected a higher resolution of (1280×720) . The evaluation was conducted on the FloodSeg validation dataset, as well as on the two test sets as it stated in Section III. Segmentation performance was measured through the mIoU (%) metric [22] considering the two classes (flood water and background), and was calculated using the following equation:

$$mIoU = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N IoU_i \quad (2)$$

with N being the total number of classes and IoU_i is computed for each class i by:

$$IoU_i = \frac{|P_i \cap M_i|}{|P_i \cup M_i|} \quad (3)$$

As far as the networks' inference speed, we measured it in milliseconds (ms) and the respective Frame-per-second rate metric (FPS). To support this process, our system is equipped with an NVIDIA GTX 1080 GPU and 16 GB of RAM. The flood segmentation performance and speed are displayed on Table I.

As it can be seen in, I all of the DNN models on average can achieve 86 – 87% mIoU performance on

the FloodSeg validation set, indicating that, while the problem is a binary, it is still challenging to achieve greater performances. Another important observation that supports our initial assumption about the need to develop a more generic supervised approach for our dataset—aimed at enhancing the generalization and physical domain adaptation of the selected models—is highlighted by the models’ consistent performance, maintaining accuracy above 80% when tested on real-world flood videos.

Fig. 5. Segmentation examples from the FloodSeg validation set using the PSPNet architecture

Among the models, PidNet Medium achieved the highest overall performance with a mIoU of 87.77% on the FloodSeg dataset and 85.14% on the Italian dataset, demonstrating superior accuracy in diverse environments. However, it exhibited the slowest processing speed at 8.49 ms per frame and the lowest frame rate of 117.78 FPS, indicating a trade-off between accuracy and speed. CNN-I2I closely followed with a mIoU of 87.65% on FloodSeg and balanced performance across datasets, achieving the highest frame rate of 153.44 FPS due to its relatively fast processing speed of 6.52 ms, making it well-suited for real-time applications. PSPNet showed competitive accuracy, particularly excelling on the Greek dataset with a mIoU of 82.94%, the highest in that category, but maintained moderate processing speed (6.62 ms) and frame rate (150.87 FPS). On the other hand, PidNet Small offered the fastest processing at 3.25 ms and the highest frame rate of 307.71 FPS, highlighting its efficiency. However, this came at the cost of slightly lower accuracy, especially on the Greek dataset (e.g., 77.87%).

If computational capabilities allow, we recommend selecting PSPNet as it demonstrates greater stability in segmentation results across different test sets. Additionally, PSPNet is capable of generating higher-resolution masks compared to CNN-I2I, which produces downsam-

TABLE I
mIoU (%) PERFORMANCE OF THE SUPERVISED FLOOD WATER SEGMENTATION MODELS.

Model	Selected Test Set			Performance	
	FloodSeg	Greek	Italian	Speed (ms)	FPS
CNN-I2I	87.65	81.48	83.07	6.52	153.44
PSPNet	87.49	82.94	81.84	6.62	150.87
PidNet Small	86.10	77.87	84.09	3.25	307.71
PidNet Medium	87.77	81.87	85.14	8.49	117.78

pled output masks that may introduce noise during post-processing. Furthermore, the three-branch architecture of PIDNet, while powerful, can sometimes challenge the adaptability of semi-supervised methods. Figure 5 shows a subset of three data samples from the FloodSeg validation set, alongside the predicted flood segmentation masks and the ground truth masks. The visual comparison between the predicted and ground truth segmentation masks highlights the model’s ability to capture fine details and boundaries, demonstrating its high accuracy and effectiveness.

B. Semi-Supervised Flood Water Segmentation Architecture

As it is already stated in Section II, some researchers tried to address the data scarcity on the flood domain, by including regular waterbody images in their datasets, thus making flood a ”minority” concept. Our strategy in this matter was to make use of thousands of unlabeled flood images that were available publicly, like the dataset published in [14]. Therefore, we explored the use of semi-supervised training to help the models generalize more effectively, enabling them to capture a broader range of landscapes and variations, including subtle differences in water hue.

Popular semi-supervised training methods for semantic segmentation are reviewed thoroughly in [23]. In our study, we opted for a self-training method, namely ST++ [24], which is deemed to be a straightforward and efficient way to leverage unlabeled data. This method utilizes a teacher network, trained with the labeled images, to predict pseudo-labels for the available unlabeled images. These pseudo-labels are considered to be the ground truth for the respective images, and a student network can then be trained using both labeled and unlabeled images. In order to avoid overfitting noisy labels produced by the teacher, strong image perturbations are applied in the unlabeled images.

Researchers in [24] have also proposed a method to implement self-training at two stages, by separating the unlabeled images into a reliable and an unreliable set. Suppose that we have K checkpoints of a trained teacher model, obtained from supervised training. We predict the segmentation pseudo-masks M_{ij}^K for each image i .

Then, the image reliability score, s_i , which tags reliable and unreliable images is calculated as follows:

$$s_i = \sum_{j=1}^{K-1} \text{meanIoU}(\mathbf{M}_{ij}, \mathbf{M}_{iK}) \quad (4)$$

After this separation, the teacher model produces pseudo-labels for the reliable set first, which is incorporated into training to obtain a better teacher model. The process is repeated with the unreliable set, and finally, a student model is trained using all labeled and unlabeled images. In our work we experimented with the two-staged method as proposed in [24], since it was proven through experimentation that it enhances even more the flood water segmentation performance. We adopted PSPnet as both teacher and student network, and Colorjitter, Random Grayscale, Blur, and Cutout [25] image perturbations were applied in the unlabeled images.

Fig. 6. Visualized segmentation maps from the PSPNet architecture, showcasing data samples extracted from the three test videos, demonstrating the model’s ability to accurately differentiate and effectively segment the flood from the background.

1) *Performance Analysis:* In the final set of experiments, we trained PSPNet in a semi-supervised setting to help the model generalize better in dynamic flood disaster environments. To efficiently monitor the impact of the number of unlabeled images on the overall mIoU performance, we created a split of the original unlabeled set, consisting of 827, 2430, and 4647 images, respectively. To this end, three experiments were made, using these three unlabeled sets. A detailed evaluation of the resulting models can be seen in Table II. Comparisons can be made between those three experiments, as well as with the supervised-only PSPnet results presented in Table I. The inclusion of unlabeled images in PSPNet training led to significantly better flood water segmentation performance across all validation and test sets, particularly in the Greek flood video. We firmly believe that this observation further strengthens our initial

assumption that a general-purpose flood segmentation dataset can efficiently improve the generalization performance of segmentation models across diverse landscapes. Additionally, this is important because the flood water segmentation task lacks large labeled datasets, while unlabeled images are broadly available online. As for the number of unlabeled images, it is important to note that increasing their amount improves the mIoU score on the FloodSeg validation set. However, this is not the case for the Greek and Italian test sets, where the PSPNet trained with fewer unlabeled images seems to generalize better. This suggests that even with a smaller portion of unlabeled samples, the models can still achieve reasonably good performance.

TABLE II
mIoU (%) OF THE SEMI-SUPERVISED ST++ METHOD APPLIED WITH PSPNET ARCHITECTURE.

Unlabeled Images Quantity	FloodSeg Test Set	Greek Test Set	Italian Test Set
827	88.43	86.06	84.36
2430	88.74	86.55	83.88
4647	88.94	86.51	83.89

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduce an efficient flood monitoring system aimed at providing valuable responses in the natural disaster management domain. Using a novel dataset, we trained and evaluated various semantic segmentation deep neural network architectures for the flood water segmentation task. The selected models are capable of operating in real-time, processing large volumes of flood footage, and producing segmentation masks to aid in precise event mapping. Additionally, we incorporated thousands of unlabeled images into the training process through a semi-supervised self-training method to further enhance the generalization ability of the proposed DNN models. The resulting models achieved improved scores on all validation and test sets, offering a reliable flood monitoring solution capable of analyzing large volumes of visual flood data from multiple sensors.

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